

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE EMERGENCE OF DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

Nizomov Akmal Saidolimovich

Master student of pedagogy and psychology of International Asian university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10674789>

Abstract. *In this article, an attempt was made to reveal the leading criteria, such as the description of the manifestations of deviant behavior, the negative consequences of deviant behavior, and the manifestations of social norms.*

Keywords: *destructive behavior, deviant behavior, delinquent behavior, eros, thanatos, chromosome theory, endocrine theory, biological theory, destructive institution.*

Fundamental socio-economic and political reforms, comprehensive works being carried out in our republic to build a developed legal-democratic state, a free civil society, are a vivid expression of the care shown to the youth, who are the owners of our tomorrow and, moreover, our future.

In the current process of globalization, it is important and urgent to avoid attacks aimed at occupying the consciousness of the individual, to form a strong spirituality in everyone's mind, to protect young people from the influence of destructive groups, to create ideological immunity in the mind of every citizen in our society based on our national and spiritual values, anti-manipulative, assertive behavior in ensuring security. It is one of the issues of occupation. This is one of the factors that will serve as a guarantee for the safety of the individual, as well as the safety of the society and the state in the future.

The urgency of this problem is justified by the need to create the scientific basis of protection against destructive ideas, to study the content of activity, working methods, propaganda methods and tools of destructive groups using scientific methods, and to develop a mechanism of social-psychological protection from them. To analyze the activities of destructive religious, cultural, extremist and terrorist currents and groups, which have a negative impact on the stability of the Republic of Uzbekistan, more precisely, on its social and spiritual development, to define and classify the genesis, essence and content of the concepts of destructive groups and ideas based on existing scientific theories. , creating a certain socio-psychological basis so that young people do not fall under the influence of these ideas is one of the important tasks facing psychology, pedagogy and all social and humanitarian sciences. This issue, that is, the problem of young people being influenced by destructive ideas, was not a separate object of research. From this point of view, the socio-psychological study of the reasons for the emergence of destructive ideas and groups, the expansion of the sphere of activity, is of actual theoretical and practical importance.

Identifying young people who have a tendency to join psychologically and pedagogically destructive groups, and carrying out educational work with them, are some of the tasks that need to be carried out today. Another relevant aspect of the issue is that youth is one of the main subjects of security. They make it possible to study the safety of a person from a socio-psychological point of view, to determine what social, economic, political, informational-psychological, cultural, ideological effects need to be paid attention to in order to ensure safety. In turn, these will serve to enrich the content of program activities planned within the framework of the State policy on youth adopted in our country.

The nature of destructive behavior in humans is considered one of the problems that have not been well studied in the science of psychology. This problem was formed in the middle of the 20th century. The psychological approach is based on distinguishing the social-psychological difference of individual manifestations of deviant behavior. Psychological classifications are based on the following criteria:

- type of violated norm;
- morality and its psychological purpose in motivation;
- the consequences of this behavior and the damage it causes;
- a personal-methodical description of ethics.

It should be noted that the term "deviant behavior" can be applied to children under the age of 5, and strictly speaking, we can use it after the age of 9. Before the age of 5, the child does not have the necessary ideas about social norms, and self-control is carried out with the help of adults. Only at the age of 9-10, it is possible to talk about the ability of a child to independently observe social norms. If the behavior of children younger than 5 years deviates significantly from the age norm, then it is appropriate to consider it as a manifestation of immaturity, nervous reaction or mental development disorder.

Destructive behavior is manifested in 2 main types:

1. The delinquent type is the orientation of behavior to actions that are contrary to the social and legal norms accepted in society.
2. The deviant type is the manifestation of moral views contrary to the moral standards accepted in society.

In all forms of destructive behavior, it occurs as a certain protective reaction of a person, but it can be associated with disorders in the nervous system. Destructive behavior can be caused by negative emotional experiences in childhood, emotional coldness of parents towards the child, lack of love from them at the necessary time, and hereditary factors.

Z. Freud states that there are 2 main instincts in human behavior: Eros is the instinct of life. The power in it directs to preservation and restoration of life. Thanatos is the death instinct. Its power directs to destroy and stop life.

Destructive behavior is common to all people. In some people, this behavior is so strong that it determines their position and behavior in society. In the manifestation of destructive behavior, negative assumptions are formed as a result of negative attitudes of a person towards the majority of people around him. S.P. Ivanov and V.V. In Boyko's studies, the following types of destructive devices are distinguished:

1. Hidden ruthlessness in thoughts and actions towards others;
2. Open cruelty towards others;
3. Based on negative thoughts about people. It is the same with having a negative opinion about the people who caused it based on the circumstances that arose in certain social situations;
4. Making unfounded generalizations about one's partners due to negative factors.

Another direction of biological theories of aggression is related to the study of the role of hormonal influences on criminal and aggressive behavior. In 1924, the American scientist M. Schlapp studied the endocrine system of criminals, he found that one-third of the prisoners he examined suffered from emotional instability.

We see that the various manifestations of a person's deviant behavior are located on the single axis of "destructive morality" directed against himself or others.

The first and most important institution of social control in human education is the family. A healthy family environment plays an important role in raising a child and forming a mature generation. A child lives in a family environment from the day of birth. Family traditions, values, and customs form a child's personality. The most important thing is that children understand and feel the demands of society through the school of family life. The place and role of the direct officials and heads of organizations for educational processes is great for the formation of the personal views of the members of the society, for the composition of their socially active attitudes towards deviant behavior. "It is possible for some, it is not possible for others", "good now, bad tomorrow" and similar attitudes are very dangerous to act in the form of secondary behavior, that is, in the direction of parallel standards. Therefore, violation of the norms of behavior by officials, leaders of various public organizations and labor unions, pedagogues and educators, and representatives of law enforcement organizations is strictly condemned in any case.

Each of the social evils related to alcoholism, drug addiction, and suicide, which are deviant behaviors, have essentially different aspects according to their occurrence and social consequences. The first difference is that the long-term continuation of socially harmful habits is that deviant behavior becomes an integral part of the lifestyle. Constant family disagreements, dissatisfaction with the family and environment, misunderstandings at home, etc. - all this hurts the psyche of the subject and he tries to change the existing situation. In the current process of globalization, the risk of young people falling under the influence of values propagated by various destructive groups and ideas is increasing. After all, the formation of necessary, important life values and directions is a very complex process, which is formed based on existing traditions and procedures, and not through voluntary efforts or instructions. The important life plans of young people depend on the nature of the areas of vital importance for them. Life-important directions are formed on the basis of the environment around young men and women, the value system specific to their loved ones. The environment close to the youth, and the individuals, are individuals who have taken on the unique, modern youth subculture. Depending on the extent to which the socio-philosophical nature of the youth subculture, the characteristics of the value structure, as well as the extent to which the aspects of possible deformation of their life directions have been analyzed, it is possible to think about psychological-pedagogical influence and psychological-pedagogical support for them.

Modern young people have different values and orientations, and a number of external factors, such as socialization and upbringing of young men and women, play an important role in their formation. In such conditions, different persons may have different life positions. Some young people adapt to social life very easily, while others find it very difficult.

Psychological-pedagogical impact on the representatives of the younger generation, supporting them psychologically-pedagogically is important in a number of aspects. First of all, it should be noted that young people are the main driving force and perspective of all societies. As the formation of the personality of young people coincides with the time of complex political, social, and economic changes in the whole world, the support of the older generation will certainly be necessary for their proper upbringing. Providing the necessary psychological and pedagogical advice and support to boys and girls, forming appropriate behavioral skills in them, directing their energy to themselves, protecting their minds from the influence of destructive ideas is one of the important factors of ensuring the safety of the individual, state and society.

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